

ated at the ACRI experimental farm, Madurai, to determine population fluctuations and peak emergence of rice gall midge *Orseolia oryzae* (Wood-Mason). The data will help scientists predict pest occurrence and insecticide applications.

The earliest gall midge capture was in the second week of Aug. Populations gradually increased until mid-Oct, then declined (see figure). Peak occurrence coincided with the maximum tillering phase of the rice crop. □

Adult midges collected in a bamboo light-trap with a 40-watt bulb, Madurai, India, 1981-82.

Insecticide toxicity to natural brown planthopper enemies

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We investigated contact toxicity of some foliar insecticides on brown planthopper predators: the mirid bug *Cyrtorhinus lividipennis* Reuter and spiders, *Lycosa* sp., that inhabit the rice ecosystem

Two 10-day-old TN1 seedlings were planted in clay pots. Plants were sprayed with insecticides 20 days after planting; 24 h later 10 adult mirid bugs (5 males and 5 females) were released per pot and confined in mylar cages. To prevent the predators from starving, three to four BPH nymphs were released in each pot.

Twenty spiderlings were forced to crawl over a chemical solution film in a

Toxicity of insecticides to brown planthopper predators.^a

Insecticide	Corrected mortality ^b (%)	
	<i>C. lividipennis</i>	<i>Lycosa</i> sp.
Decamethrin 0.002%	100 a	98 a
Methyl parathion 0.04%	100 a	98 a
Cypermethrin 0.002%	93 a	93 a
Fenvalerate 0.002%	93 a	92 a
Quinalphos 0.04%	93 a	92 a
Phosalone 0.04%	93 a	92 a
Permethrin 0.002%	92 a	90 a
Fenthion 0.04%	85 ab	90 a
Methamidophos 0.04%	76 b	87 ab
Phosphamidon 0.04%	76 b	79 b
FMC35001 0.04%	76 b	74 b

^a Mean of 3 replications. ^b Analysis based on arcsin/percentage values. Means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at 5% level.

large petri dish for 2 min then immediately transferred to glass tubes which were covered with muslin. Predator mortality was recorded 24 h after treatment.

Decamethrin and methyl parathion caused 100% *C. lividipennis* mortality,

closely followed by cypermethrin, fenvalerate, quinalphos, phosalone, and permethrin (see table). All insecticides tested were highly toxic to spiderlings. Mortality ranged from 74% (FMC35001) to 98% (decamethrin and methyl parathion). □

Pest management and control WEEDS

Sawdust-mulching for controlling weeds in transplanted summer rice

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Weeds are a major constraint to successful summer rice cultivation in Assam. Sawdust mulch 0, 2, and 4 cm thick was tested for weed control on Pusa 33, Mairang, and Ngoba in a split-plot design with 4 replications. On 25 Apr, 25-day-old seedlings were transplanted in 20 × 15 cm

Table 1. Fresh weight of weeds per 1.8 m² in rice fields with different sawdust mulching.

Variety	Fresh wt (g) of weeds			Mean ^a
	0	2-cm mulch	4-cm mulch	
Pusa 33	960	700	720	793.3 b
Mairang	2790	1466	853	1703.0 a
Ngoba	1100	1016	866	944.0 b
Mean ^a	1616.7 a	1060.7 b	873.0 c	

^a Any two means followed by different letters are significantly different at 5% level of probability.

spacing on 9-m² plots. At land preparation, 80 kg N, 21.5 kg P, and 33 kg K/ha were applied. Weed samples were col-

lected from 1.8-m² strips from each plot. Mulching significantly suppressed weed growth (Table 1). Weed weights

differed in different rice varieties, but interaction between mulching and variety was not significant (Table 2). Less weed weight was associated with Pusa 33, which may be because it produces more tillers and forms a more complete canopy than the two tall varieties. Mulching did not significantly increase yield. The following weed species, in order of frequency, were observed: *Echinochloa colona* (L.) Link, *Ludwigia octovalvis* (Jacq., Raven), *Cyperus iria* L., *Eclipta prostrata* (L.) L., *Cynodon dactylon* (L.) Pers., *Fimbristylis miliacea*

Table 2. Rice yield in different treatments of sawdust mulching.

Variety	Rice yield (t/ha)			
	0	2-cm mulch	4-cm mulch	Mean
Pusa 33	3.4	4.8	4.6	4.3
Mairang	1.9	2.2	2.1	2.1
Ngoba	3.0	3.4	3.2	3.2
Mean	2.8	3.5	3.3	

(L.) Vahl, *Eleusine indica* (L.) Gaertn., *Digitaria longiflora* (Retz.) Pers., *Commelina benghalensis* L., *Vernonia cinerea*

(L.) Less., *Cyperus pilosus* Vahl, *Dactyloctenium aegyptium* (L.) Beauv., and *Cyperus rotundus* L. □

Effect of azolla inoculation on weed growth in wetland rice

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Azolla has been reported to suppress weed growth in rice. A field experiment to determine the effect of azolla on growth of *Echinochloa* spp. in flooded rice was conducted in a randomized block design with three replications during 1981-82 samba. Co 43 (TNAU17005) was grown. One week after transplanting, *Azolla pinnata* was inoculated at 100, 150, 200, 250, 300, 350, 400, 450, and 500 g/m². A basal amount of 50 kg P/ha and 50 kg K/ha in 3 splits were applied.

Growth of *Echinochloa glabrescens*, *E. stagnina*, *E. crus-galli*, and *E. colona* was observed. Weeds were allowed to grow for 40 days, then fields were

Effect of azolla inoculation on weed growth in wetland rice.

Azolla inoculation (g/m ²)	Fresh weed weight ^a (kg/7.5-m ² plot)	% reduction over control	Grain yield (t/ha)
100	2.9	47	6.1
150	2.6	51	6.3
200	1.8	67	6.2
250	2.1	62	6.0
300	2.2	60	6.2
350	1.9	66	6.1
400	1.4	74	6.0
450	1.0	81	6.5
500	1.3	76	6.6
30 kg N/ha	5.7	—	6.4
Uninoculated control	5.4	—	3.6
LSD = 1.2		LSD = 1.3	
Significant at 1% level.			

^a *Echinochloa glabrescens*, *E. colona*, *E. stagnina*, *E. crus-galli*.

weeded and weed fresh weight was recorded (see table). Azolla was incorporated 41 days after planting, with 2 more incorporations at 21-day intervals. Grain yield was recorded.

Weed growth was significantly reduced

in azolla-inoculated plots, especially in those with higher inoculation levels (see table). The rapid growth and multiplication of azolla limited weed growth and probably altered gas exchange, light penetration, and temperature. □

Pest management and control

NEMATODES

Dissemination of rice root nematode through rice seedlings

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Rice root nematode *Hirschmanniella oryzae* causes up to 25% yield losses in flooded rice. This migratory endoparasite embeds itself in and feeds on root tissue.

We studied the movement of root nematode from the nursery to the field by seedlings on farmer fields on the Cauvery Delta in Tamil Nadu.

Random samples of ADT31 rice seedlings and soil from 24 flooded wet season nurseries untreated with pesticides were collected from Cauvery Delta village. Ten 23- to 25-day-old seedlings were pulled from each nursery bed and a core soil sample was taken. Number of

nematodes was estimated by Baermann pan technique using 250 g soil and 5 g rice root.

All but one nursery were infested by *H. oryzae*. Population ranged from 6 to 86 (mean 10.74) nematodes/250 g soil and 3 to 148 (mean 30.42) nematodes/5 g of root. Mean (wet) weight of the roots was 1.2 g/seedling and the mean number of nematodes per infested seedling at planting ranged from 0.60 to 29.60 (mean 7.03). These data indicate the importance of using chemicals to control nematodes in the nursery or a root dip before planting rice seedlings. □